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Sentinel-1 for Granada coast landslides monitoring and potential damage assessment

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The InSAR technique has been proved to be a powerful tool in order to detect, monitoring and analyse movements related to geological phenomena. Its application ranges from regional/national scale to a very detailed scale, up to a single building analysis. Moreover, since 2014, the free and constant availability of Sentinel-1 data has been helping the tendency of using more and more this technique in the institutional risk management activities. Many European and national projects have been financed in order to investigate and improve the processing performances and broaden the operational use and application of the results. In this work, we present the first results developed in the framework of the project Riskcoast (SOE3/P4/E0868) over an area of around 4 km² in Andalucía (Spain), including the city and the coast of Granada. Riskcoast has been funded by the Interreg Sudoe Programme through the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF). The presented work is as an example of multi scale (medium to large) application of InSAR for geohazard applications. The velocity map including the estimation of the displacement time series have been produced over the whole area by processing 139 radar images of the Sentinel-1 (A and B). Starting from those results a rapid and semi-automatic extraction of the most significant active displacement areas (ADA) has been performed. Then, after a classification of the detected areas, a more detailed analysis has been done over some selected costal landslides. Over those landslides a damage mapping has been generated based on field surveys, and then analysed together with the spatial gradient of displacement derived by the InSAR results. The Riskcoast project will be introduced and the first results presented.